

Role of Yoga Prana Vidya Protocols as Complementary Medicine for Female Reproductive System: A Successful Confirmed Pregnancy Case of IVF Patient

Shweta N. Nayak¹, Falguni Shah², Venkata Satyanarayana Nanduri³

¹YPV Level 2 & Level 3 trainer, Pune, Maharashtra, India

²YPV HDP1 healer, Pune, Maharashtra, India

³Consultant, Research & Publications, Yoga Prana Vidya Ashram, Sri Ramana Trust, Thally-635118 Tamilnadu, India

ABSTRACT

Introduction: Infertility is a sensitive problem, but only few couples access assisted reproductive technologies (ART), such as IVF (In vitro fertilization). Research shows that the success rate of any ART procedure is below 30% at best. This paper presents a patient case of two unsuccessful IVF attempts by a couple, but in the third attempt of IVF they achieved successful pregnancy using Yoga Prana Vidya (YPV) intervention as complementary modality.

Method: This paper uses case method going through medical reports, healers' reports and patient's and patient's relative's feedback on the results.

Results: After 3 weeks of daily YPV healings, the subject's 3rd attempt of IVF was successful, evidenced by the Ultrasound report confirming two fetuses. The subject's health parameters were normal.

Conclusion: Integrated Yoga Prana Vidya (YPV) system of healing and practice protocols have been helping the patients holistically to normalise their condition in physical, mental and emotional dimensions. YPV is simple yet very versatile system of proven protocols as complementary and alternative medicine, and it is recommended for all healthcare professionals to learn and practice YPV to complement in their areas of specialisation. Further research on application of YPV for improving human reproduction system may be conducted on appropriate sample to study the results on wider population.

KEYWORDS: Yoga Prana Vidya System ®, YPV ®, Complementary & alternative medicine (CAM), Human reproductive system, Assisted reproductive technology (ART), In-vitro Fertilization (IVF)

ARTICLE DETAILS

Published On:
16 June 2022

Available on:
<https://ijpbms.com/>

INTRODUCTION

Infertility is a disease of the human reproduction system that affects nearly 15 % of the reproductive age group couples worldwide, and according to WHO estimates, prevalence of primary infertility in India is between 3.9 % and 16.8%, which varies from region to region. [1].

Infertility is a global problem, but only a minority of couples access assisted reproductive technologies (ART), such as IVF (In vitro fertilization) due to financial and sociocultural barriers. Complementary and alternative medicine are seen as another option. [2]

There is limited evidence of the effectiveness of complementary and alternative medicine on improving the chances of conception and live births. Owing to the generally sub-optimal quality and heterogeneous nature of the evidence, rigorous studies are needed to determine the impact of complementary and alternative medicine on fertility.[2]

In the United States, infertility is a significant problem which affects 7–17% of all couples seeking to have children. Because of the expense associated with assisted reproductive technologies, some infertile couples turn to complementary or alternative medicine (CAM) in an attempt to become pregnant using treatment that they may perceive as being

Role of Yoga Prana Vidya Protocols as Complementary Medicine for Female Reproductive System: A Successful Confirmed Pregnancy Case of IVF Patient

lower cost, safer, or more effective. Examples of CAM that been described as treatments for infertility include pelvic physical therapy, hypnosis, yoga, homeopathy, spiritual healing, as well as acupuncture and herbal therapy. [3]

A study in USA concluded that a very low minority of infertile couples utilize CAM treatments. CAM was chosen most commonly by wealthier couples, those not achieving a pregnancy, and those with a baseline belief in the effectiveness of CAM treatments. [3].

ART (Assisted Reproductive Technology) would be taken to encompass all techniques that attempt to obtain a pregnancy by manipulating the sperm or/ and oocyte outside the body, and transferring the gamete or embryo into the uterus. The technology of In-vitro Fertilization-Embryo Transfer (IVF-ET) is the fertilization of an ovum outside the body and the transfer of the fertilized ovum to the uterus of a woman. It is stated that the success rate of any ART procedure is below 30% under the best of circumstances [4].

Factors significantly associated with primary infertility were higher educational level, employment, staying in nuclear family and high socioeconomic condition. In the recent past, due to rapid urbanization, elevated standard of living, rise in education status, women are becoming more independent and are following the trends of modern lifestyle. This appraisal of socioeconomic status of women has contributed to modified dietary habits, physical inactivity, which is considered to be the risk factors of developing primary infertility. Lower socioeconomic status is one of the risk factors for infertility.[5]

In addition, researchers in one study in India found that the prevalence of primary infertility increases by aging, higher BMI, irregular menstrual pattern, and family history of infertility. The changing trends of society in India such as increasing level of education and priorities of life prolong the age at marriage. Most of the literature suggests that delayed age at marriage is one of the factors for primary infertility. Obesity is another major risk factor for infertility, together with associated hormonal imbalance and menstrual dysfunction, directly affecting the female reproductive function. History of infertility among close relatives, i.e., mothers and sisters is considered one of the important risk factors for infertility. Women having family history of infertility are at higher chances of developing infertility problems mainly due to inherent genetic diseases. In addition,

menstrual hygiene plays an important role in primary fertility. Unhygienic menstrual practices such as reusing cotton clothes, washing them without soap and with unclean water, social taboos and restrictions force drying indoors, away from sunlight, and open-air predisposes to lower reproductive tract infections, irregular menstrual cycles, and ultimately infertility. [5].

Several studies have revealed that anxiety has a negative effect on fertility. The women with long-standing infertility suffer more from nervousness, panic attacks, agitation, and intolerance. Infertility affects psychological well-being of women. All these factors cause a negative impact on fertility and also aggravate the situation of infertility. As the duration of infertility increases, the level of anxiety among women also increases leading to a vicious cycle. A study found that stress and depression were significantly associated with infertility. [5].

As per other studies, the prevalence of stress among infertile women is high. In traditional country like India, childbearing is an important milestone for healthy marital life. Infertile women experience negative social consequence, including marital instability, stigmatization, and abuse. It could have a serious effect on both psychological well-being and social status of women. Various problems such as health issues, sexual distress, frustration, emotional distress, and marital problems increase with infertility and build up the stress. The stress levels rise high as the duration of infertility increases. [5].

Yoga Prana Vidya System

Yoga Prana Vidya System is a no-touch and a no-drug energy healing modality which also works at a distance and can cure many physical or psychological problems. It is an integrated and a holistic system which promotes happiness and good health at physical, emotional and mental levels using breathing, healing techniques, meditation and yoga. In the healing techniques, the healer removes the diseased, dirty or the used-up energy from the affected part and the affected chakrams of the patient and fills it up with fresh energy. The main advantage of using Yoga Prana Vidya healing techniques is, firstly that the patient need not be physically present in front of the healer as the healing can be done from a distance, and secondly, it can cure many psychological ailments too which are emotional or mental in nature.

Fig 1: Energy body of a healthy person

Fig 2: Energy body of a sick person

Role of Yoga Prana Vidya Protocols as Complementary Medicine for Female Reproductive System: A Successful Confirmed Pregnancy Case of IVF Patient

Fig 3: Chakrams in the energy body

The energy body, also known as aura, of a being surrounds the physical body, and it consists of an inner aura, an outer aura and health rays connecting these two. Figures 1 and 2 illustrate the energy body of a healthy person and sick person respectively. The energy body consists of chakrams (see figure 3) and 'nadis' (meridians) for receiving and distributing the Pranic energy, also known as life force. Figure 4 shows the pictures of human aura taken using GDV (Gas Discharge Visualisation) camera before and after healing and correlates with images in figures 1 and 2 respectively. The Yoga Prana Vidya system consists of self-practice modules such as physical exercises, Rhythmic yogic breathing, and meditation practices such as forgiveness sadhana and Planetary Peace Meditation. The healing process consists of several basic and advanced techniques of cleansing the chakrams and affected parts and energizing the same for desired results.

Published literature of over 40 articles shows that, by using Yoga Prana Vidya (YPV) healing techniques, many cases have been successfully treated such as, some difficult medical cases [6], Diabetes management & control [7], removing arterial block in heart without surgery [8], vision improvements for participants of an Eye Camp [9], improvements in holistic wellbeing and immunity of participants in a one-month YPV intensive programme [10], Role of Yoga Prana Vidya in first aid and emergency [11], improvements of health and immunity of senior citizens [12], speedy recovery of COVID patients [13], treatment of hypothyroidism [14], Lowering academic anxiety and enhancing academic performance of high school children [15], saving life of a snake-bitten human female [16], improvements in the cognitive abilities and social behaviour of mentally challenged children [17], managing the pain and side effects of a Hodgkin Lymphoma patient undergoing chemotherapy [18], and healing treatment of a female patient suffering from kneecap dislocation [19]. A review of published literature shows some experimental studies also conducted with successful outcomes such as improvements in the wellbeing of prisoners [20], and significant reduction in anxiety and depression in corporate employees [21].

This paper presents a case of IVF attempted twice by a couple unsuccessfully, but in the third attempt of IVF they achieved

Fig 4: GDV camera Images of energy body

successful pregnancy using Yoga Prana Vidya (YPV) intervention as complementary modality.

METHOD

This paper uses case method going through medical reports, healers' reports and patient's and patient's relative's feedback. The case report is presented below.

Case report

The subject's name is Utpala (pseudonym used to conceal identity), a female aged 34 years, a housewife currently not working and lives in a north Indian city.

Subject's Condition before YPV Healing (as on 06-03-2022)

Two IVF procedures, first one on 25 Sept 2021 and the second one on 6 Jan 2022 were unsuccessful. As per her doctor's assessment, all the parameters and sperm quality were good for her to conceive, yet the 2nd IVF attempt also failed. The couple wanted that the 3rd attempt should succeed without fail.

The subject heard about YPV from her sister-in-law who is a YPV healer who suggested to use YPV techniques and healings before 3rd IVF as she believed that it would help. She had positive hope of 3rd IVF to be successful because, as per her doctor, medically everything was fine. From YPV perspective it looked like something either at mental level or emotional level was causing the failure of pregnancy.

YPV Intervention

The subject had done PPM (Planetary Peace meditation) a couple of times earlier.

The healer sensed the energy body and the results from feeling of chakrams showed that the Solar chakram was highly congested and over-active. Throat chakram was congested but under-active. Navel and sex chakrams were weak and under-active. Basic chakram was also observed to be weak. Ajna chakram was found to be under-activated.

Details of Healings:

Prior to the 3rd IVF procedure, healing for relationship with husband was done, and full healing for her with strengthening the sex chakram, navel chakram and basic chakram was done. Throat chakram and ajna chakram were also strengthened. For self-practice the subject was advised to do forgiveness sadhana daily and at least one YPV online session.

Role of Yoga Prana Vidya Protocols as Complementary Medicine for Female Reproductive System: A Successful Confirmed Pregnancy Case of IVF Patient

After the 3rd IVF procedure, YPV psychotherapy was done and lower chakrams were monitored and cleaned and energized gently using white color prana when required. Ajna and throat chakrams were strengthened further.

Table 1 below gives an overview of the healings versus patient progress achieved.

Table 1: Healings given Vs. progress

Healing session & date	Result for the subject
Session 1: 07-03-2022	Less fearful and felt relaxed
Session 3: 09-03-2022	Cheerful and optimistic about the IVF procedure
Session 5: 11-03-2022	IVF procedure happened on 10th March. The subject feels better than the earlier 2 procedures
Session10: 21-03-2022	Didn't experience any issues still, unlike the earlier 2 IVFs
Session14: 26-03-2022	IVF was successful and she is expected with twins and advised for ultrasound on 7th April

Summary of YPV healings given and outcomes in this case:

- Subject's Health Parameters were normal at the end of Healings.
- Number of hours of night sleep on average per day was 7
- Total number of healings given were 16
- Response from healings: good feeling of the subject and positive IVF outcome
- Final status of the Subject: IVF report confirmed pregnancy with twin foetus (Figure 1 report)

Fig 1 Report dated 13 May 2022

Feedback from patient's relative dated 11 April 2022:

“I am XXXX from Pune. My sister-in-law Utpala was undergoing IVF treatment from last year. In September 2021, first implant was done, but it was unsuccessful. In January 2022 again the implant failed. She was very disappointed and sad. She said that the procedure was very painful physically. Mentally also she was getting disturbed because of repeated failures.

Again, in March 2022 the implant was planned. This time I suggested her, to start taking YPV healings before the implant. I approached the healers, as I was aware that, they had handled such a case before and the implant procedure in that case went smoothly.

Healing for her is still continuing and the healer is doing it for her. During all this time the healer guided me and my sister-in-law patiently and resolved all the queries.

Role of Yoga Prana Vidya Protocols as Complementary Medicine for Female Reproductive System: A Successful Confirmed Pregnancy Case of IVF Patient

We are thankful to her for guiding us and helping us in this difficult situation.

Thank you
XXXX “

DISCUSSION

Studies comparing the outcomes of natural versus assisted reproductive technologies (ART) pregnancies report heterogeneous results. Despite the success of ART to overcome infertility, concern is growing regarding both its safety and its effect on maternal and child health. [22].

The results of a study indicate that children born to single mothers and children of ART-treated mothers have a higher morbidity and consume more specialist care than children of married/cohabiting and naturally pregnant mothers. With the use of ART, maternal single status and advanced maternal age are risk factors of importance to consider in pediatric care and when counseling women who are considering ART treatment.[23].

In this context, Yoga Prana Vidya practice is a useful tool to assist pregnant women, either conceived naturally or assisted, to learn and use YPV healing techniques for maintaining good physical, emotional and mental health of both mother and child from the very beginning of the pregnancy journey to reduce after-birth risks.

CONCLUSION

Integrated Yoga Prana Vidya (YPV) system of healing and practice protocols helps the pregnancy seeking patient holistically to normalise their condition. YPV is simple yet very versatile system of proven protocols and it is recommended for all healthcare professionals to learn and practice YPV to complement their areas of specialisation. Further research on application of YPV for improving human reproduction system may be conducted on appropriate sample to study the results on wider population.

REFERENCES

- I. NHP (National Health Portal of India). Infertility. Available from <https://www.nhp.gov.in/disease/reproductive-system/infertility> 2016
- II. Yogasundram, H.M., Hui, A.J.O., Sia, C.Y.S. et al. Reproductive outcomes in women and men using complementary and alternative medicine treatment and not receiving artificial reproductive technology: a systematic review. *Arch Gynecol Obstet* 303, 821–835 (2021). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00404-020-05836-4>
- III. Smith JF, Eisenberg ML, Millstein SG, Nachtigall RD, Shindel AW, Wing H, Cedars M, Pasch L, Katz PP; Infertility Outcomes Program Project Group. The use of complementary and alternative fertility treatment in couples seeking fertility care: data from a prospective cohort in the United States. *Fertil Steril.* 2010 May 1;93(7):2169-74. doi: 10.1016/j.fertnstert.2010.02.054. Epub 2010 Mar 24. PMID: 20338559; P MCID: PMC2860047
- IV. ICMR/NAMS (INDIA). National Guidelines for Accreditation, Supervision and Regulation of ART Clinics in India. 2005. Available https://main.icmr.nic.in/sites/default/files/art/ART_Pdf.pdf
- V. Katole, A, Saoji, A, Prevalence of primary infertility and its associated risk factors in urban population of central India: A community-based cross-sectional study. 2019/10/1, - *Indian Journal of Community Medicine, JO - Indian J Community Med* 44 (4):337- - 341 UL - <https://www.ijcm.org.in/article.asp?issn=0970-0218;year=2019;volume=44;issue=4;page=337;epage=341;aualast=Katole;t=5DO> - 10.4103/ijcm.IJCM_7_19
- VI. Neravetla, J, Nanduri, VS. A study into the successful treatment of some difficult Medical cases using Yoga Prana Vidya (YPV) Healing System as alternative medicine. *Int J Sci Eng Res*, 2019, 10 (7):882-8877
- VII. Rajagopal AH, Ramya A, Nanduri, VS. Diabetes Management and Control Using Yoga Prana Vidya (YPV) Healing System, *Journal of Biology and Life Science ISSN 2157-6076*, 2019, Vol. 10, No. 2
- VIII. Ramya A, Nanduri, VS. Cardiac Case Study: Successful Healing Treatment of a 48-Year-Old Male with Block in Heart, Using Yoga Prana Vidya (YPV) Healing System. *Saudi J Nurs Health Care*, Nov 2019; 2(11): 353-356. <https://www.yogapranavidya.com/about-ypv-research/publications/successful-healing-treatment-of-a-48-year-old-male-with-block-in-heart-using-ypv/>
- IX. Nanduri VS, Chaitra N. How the participants of a Yoga Prana Vidya (YPV) Eye Camp experienced vision improvements: A Case study. *The Journal of Community Health Management.* (2019) 6(4): 139-146. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.18231/j.jchm.2019.028>
- X. Neravetla J, Nanduri VS. A study of the effects of Yoga Prana Vidya one-month intensive residential programme for participants on their physical health, psychological well-being and improved immunity. *International Journal of Research and Analytical Reviews (IJRAR)*, 7(2), 18-27.
- XI. Neravetla J, Nanduri, VS. Role of Yoga Prana Vidya (YPV) Healing Techniques in Emergency

Role of Yoga Prana Vidya Protocols as Complementary Medicine for Female Reproductive System: A Successful Confirmed Pregnancy Case of IVF Patient

- and First Aid: A Summary of Case Reports. *International Journal of Medical Science and Health Research*. 4(3), 133-146
- XII. Nanduri VS. Effectiveness of Yoga Prana Vidya practice protocols for health improvements and boosting immunity of seniors – A review. *J.Bio.Innov* 9(4), pp: 583-588, 2020 |ISSN 2277-8330 (Electronic)
- XIII. Nanduri VS, Karnani V. Successful and speedy recovery of COVID patients using Yoga Prana Vidya (YPV) Healing. *Covid-19 2020*; 1(4):78-82
Doi: <http://doi.org/10.18231/j.covid.2020.005>
- XIV. Revathi R, Janani N, Nanduri, VS. Successful healing treatment of Hypothyroidism using Integrated Yoga Prana Vidya (YPV) healing approach as complementary medicine: Case reports. *J Prev Med Holistic Health* 2020;6(1):1-7.
- XV. Ramya A, Kraleti P, Gopal KVT, Nanduri, VS. Efficacy of Planetary Peace Meditation (PPM) of Yoga Prana Vidya (YPV) System in Enhancing Academic Performance of High School Children: A Case study. *Indian Journal of Psychology and Education*, 10 (2), July 2020, 59-64. ISSN -2231-1432
- XVI. Ramya A, Ashwin V, Divya D, Nanduri VS. Serious snake bite case: successful treatment using yoga prana vidya (YPV) healing system. 2021; 5 (01):101-110
<http://dx.doi.org/10.51505/ijmsr.2021.5111>
DOI: 10.51505/ijmsr.2021.5111
- XVII. Rajkumari K, Bembalkar S, Nanduri VS. A Pilot Study of the Effects of Yoga Prana Vidya (YPV) protocols on social behaviour, cognitive abilities and IQ of mentally challenged children, *Pediatric Review – International Journal of Pediatric Research-2021 Volume 8 Number 1 (January-February-2021):7-15* Available From <https://pediatrics.medresearch.in/index.php/ijpr/article/view/653>
- XVIII. Jain V, Bindal S, Bhatia PK, Nanduri VS. Managing pain and side effects of a Hodgkin lymphoma female patient undergoing Chemotherapy using Yoga Prana Vidya System as complementary medicine: A case report. *International Journal of Medical Sciences and Academic Research*, v. 2, n. 05, 30 Oct. 2021.
- XIX. Dholakia M, Tandon I, Dholakia D, Nanduri, VS. "Successful Healing Treatment of Kneecap (Patellar) Dislocation of a Teen Female Patient Using Yoga Prana Vidya System Protocols without Surgery: A Case Report". *Acta Scientific Women's Health* 3.11 (2021): 15-20.
- XX. Nanduri VS, Revathi R. Effects of Yoga Prana Vidya intervention on psychological wellbeing and criminal attitude of under-trial prisoners. *Ind J Psychiatric Social Work*. 2020; 11(2).Epub.1-9
DOI:
<http://dx.doi.org/10.29120/ijpsw.2020.v11.i2.232>
- XXI. Nanduri VS. A Study on the Effects of Yoga Prana Vidya System (YPV) Intervention at workplace for Corporate Employees and Executives to alleviate Anxiety, Depression and Burnout; and participants' perceptions and experiences of the YPV Intervention. *International Journal of Indian Psychology*, 2020;8(3), 374-390. DIP:18.01.047/20200803, DOI:10.25215/0803.047
- XXII. da Silva, S.G., da Silveira, M.F., Bertoldi, A.D. *et al*. Maternal and child-health outcomes in pregnancies following Assisted Reproductive Technology (ART): a prospective cohort study. *BMC Pregnancy Childbirth* **20**, 106 (2020). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12884-020-2755-z>
- XXIII. Pettersson, M.L., Bladh, M., Nedstrand, E. et al. Maternal advanced age, single parenthood, and ART increase the risk of child morbidity up to five years of age. *BMC Pediatr* 22, 39 (2022). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12887-021-03103-2>